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Research Article

**THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL EFFECTS OF
MOTHERS FOLLOWING THEIR CHILDREN'S STUDIES
DURING THE CORONA PERIOD**¹Khalid.G.Alotibi, ²Fatima.B.Barnawi, ³Sundus.S.BukarI, ⁴Ali.Y.Alzubaidi ,
⁵Mohammed.A.Allahani, ⁶Husna.S.Altalhi.¹Senior Social Specialist, Qassim Health Complex²Social worker at Mecca Health Complex³Social worker at Mecca Health Complex⁴Social Specialist, Health Affairs Compliance Department⁵Social worker at Maternity and Children Hospital in Mecca⁶Social worker at the primary Healthcare center in Kudi and Alhijrah**Article Received:** August 2022**Accepted:** August 2022**Published:** September 2022**Abstract:**

The aim of the research is to find out what the psychological and neurological factors accompanying and influencing mothers when they have children, know the social factors also influencing and accompanying them, and whether the physical condition of a family has a role in affecting mothers psychologically and socially, and whether there are other influencing factors or not. A questionnaire was created using the Google Drive application and it was distributed electronically through the social networking service application (WhatsApp) to 700 people (men and women), and the answer was obtained from 500 people in the city of Mecca

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1- INTRODUCTION:

Mental health is considered one of the most important goals pursued by psychologists, as it makes a person live a healthy life full of psychological balance and peace with himself and others, which makes him achieve Success in various aspects of his life, and achieving his desires and goals in the best ways, as well as avoiding it the trouble of conflicts and tension, and the psychological disturbances and problems they lead to ⁽¹⁾, the more a person enjoys good psychological health, the more he is able to confront and overcome life's crises ⁽²⁾. Distance education during the Coronavirus pandemic is one of the crises causing many psychological stresses, which can negatively affect mothers, who may be exposed to infection the mother may face disorders and diseases that pose a threat to their psychological health The process of teaching her children during distance education includes many situations that include unrelated events, and the reason is due to the impact of these situations on mental health in particular for mothers of primary school students. At the level of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, made a rapid transition to using alternative distance education, providing the curriculum to all male and female students at various levels Students can study from their homes, using technological programs containing platforms specific educational and virtual classes according to a study plan and a well-studied period of time ⁽³⁾. and after declaring a state of emergency in the countries of the world and closing schools and educational institutions to transform learning into distance learning, taking care of the mental health of mothers has become such a necessity Crises are very important and difficult at the same time, as mothers have become. There are many obstacles in this crisis that affect their personalities and behavior, as well ⁽⁴⁾ mentioned that mental health is one of the most important factors. The basics that help the individual maintain healthy harmony in his personality and behavior, the inability of the individual to achieve this psychological harmony causes disturbances and problems that affect. It then leads to intervention and treatment. In addition to this, the long-term impact of this pandemic extends through the mothers, children, and then on their families, where many changes and reactions began to appear behaviors of individuals, as mentioned in a study ⁽⁵⁾. The changes brought about by the pandemic Corona in normal life have caused psychological, behavioral, and physical changes in individuals. All of this negatively affects them if this influence is unbalanced and exceeds their capacity and their health and psychological ability, but if this change is positive and balanced, and she is able the mother should create a good environment compatible with her health and

ability to help her overcome this crisis. In compliance with precautionary measures to limit the spread of the virus, schools were closed all around the world, and resorting to distance education, making increased the daily tasks that are it is the responsibility of mothers, whether they are working or housewives, such as arranging, cooking and caring and child care, and the pandemic added intensive sterilization of surfaces and frequent hand washing, which this resulted in the occurrence of psychological crises, as confirmed by the study ⁽⁶⁾. Married females during the pandemic are more affected by psychological problems compared to unmarried females. ⁽⁷⁾ study stated that the level of mental health during a pandemic Corona is very low, which confirms the negative impact that the pandemic has had on Mental Health ⁽⁸⁾, given the novelty of the pandemic and the lack of studies on this issue.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study went on in (the city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), started the research and then writing the question in April 2022, and the study ended with data collection in September 2022. The examiner used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the cultural phenomenon, and (The psychological and social effects of mothers following their children's studies during the coronavirus period). This type of study is described by analysis, cause, topicality, and certainly, as it is worried about personals and communities, as it learns the changeable and their impacts on the health of the personage culture, and consumer, the expand of illness and their bonds to demographic differentiable such as age, sex, nationality, and married status. Status, function (1), and use of the Office Group 2010 histogram for Excel to rank the results by dragging them on the statistical software (2).

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A questionnaire is an important and useful device for raising a huge amount of data However, researchers were not allowed to personally meet participants in the online research, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent contagion between participants and examiners and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only replied to the question electronically, because the questionnaire contains twelve closed questions. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere (3), As for the ages of the participants in the response to the research questionnaire, their ages were as follows: 16-23 years 4.4%, 24-31 years old 30.4%, 32-39 years old 21.7%,

40-47 years old 26.1%, 48 -55 years was 17.4%. As for the gender of the research participants, they were as follows: 41.3% male and 58.7% female. As for the nationality of the participants, 97.8% were Saudis while non-Saudis were 2.2%. As for the occupation of the male participants, it was as follows: Student 3%, government employee 56.7%, private sector employee 23.3%, self-employed person 7%, 10% of participants do not work at all. For women's professions, they were as follows: student 3.3%, government employee 69%, private sector employee 0%, self-employed women 7%, housewives (not working) 20.7%. Regarding the first question: Do you think that there are factors that psychologically influence mothers to pursue their children's education and achievement, such as lack of time, controlling young children, and feeling helpless? The answers were as follows: yes 69.1%, no 10.9%, and I don't know 20%. As for the second question: Do they exhibit psychological problems such as nervousness, agitation, tension, anxiety, and physical fatigue while monitoring their children? Participants answered yes by 91.3%, no by 6.7%, and I don't know by 2%. The third question: In your opinion, do nervousness and irritability affect mothers' focus on monitoring their children's achievements? The answers were yes 93.5%, no 6.5%, and I don't know 0%. The fourth question was: Do nervousness and irritability affect their concentration to a significant and obvious degree when monitoring their children's achievement? The answers were as follows: Yes 76.1%, No 19.6%, I don't know 4.3%. The fifth question about Do you think that it is better to enroll mothers in educational and counseling courses in this regard in the field of following up on their children's studies? The answers were yes 87%, and those who said no and I do not know are equal to 6.5%, The sixth question about Do you think that the separation of parents affects psychological and social on achievement Are your children poorly academically?

Yes 87%, No 8.7%, I don't know 4.3%. The seventh question was: In your opinion, does the death of one of the parents affect the children's academic achievement psychologically and socially? Yes, 84.8%, while the answers "no" and "I don't know" were equal at a rate of 7.6%. The eighth question was about which of these following factors affect mothers in monitoring their children's academic achievement. Nervousness and nervousness, lack of time, divorce, all of the above, financial condition, ignorance, Busy preparing food for the family?

The answers were: nervousness and nervousness 8.7%, lack of time 13%, divorce 8.7%, all of the above 58.7%, financial condition 6%, ignorance 0%, and preoccupation with preparing family food 4.9%. The ninth question: In your opinion, is it better for fathers to leave the academic achievement of children to fathers than to mothers? The answers were 21.7%, no 67.4%, and I don't know 10.9%. The tenth question: In your opinion, does the financial condition of the family have a role on the academic impact of children? The answers were yes 64.4%, no 31.1%, and I don't know 4.5%. As for the last question: Do you think that mothers in the current period no longer have the patience and patience to follow up on their children's studies? The answers were yes 56.5%, no 30.4%, and I don't know 13%. Through the participants' answers, we found that agitation, nervousness, tension, anxiety, and physical fatigue affect them by a rate of 91.3%, and nervousness also affects them by a rate of 93.5%, which is considered a very high percentage. After the couple's divorce comes, it affects them by a rate of 87%, and when the participants are asked about their financial condition, does it affect their When mothers receive their children's academic achievement, they report that it affects them by 64.4% (thinking about the financial situation represents a major concern for them).(figure No.1)

Figure No.1: Participants' opinions about the mother's psychological state, such as nervousness, agitation, tension, anxiety, and physical fatigue, while monitoring their children

CONCLUSION:

We find that the conclusion of the current study is that nervousness and irritability affect the psychological and nervous state of mothers while they are teaching their children. This is the same result of the Amal Mubarakhi 2023 study in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, where she stated in her study that the previous factors. On mothers and fathers, mental health problems such as nervousness, agitation, tension, anxiety, and these problems affected and caused negative and positive behaviors; the study recommended physical fatigue. To create guidance programs to train mothers on modern educational methods.

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